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**Introducing an Effective Cybercrime Regime
for Sri Lanka: A Comparative Analysis**

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LETTER OF RECOMMENDATION

The dissertation titled "Introducing An Effective Cybercrime Regime for Sri Lanka: A Comparative Analysis" submitted by Mr. M. M. G. Niranjana Weerakumara Meegammana has been supervised by me and I have found the dissertation to be in conformity with the required standard prescribed by the Faculty of Law, University of Colombo. Therefore, it is recommended for evaluation.

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Abstract

"Cybercrime is the greatest threat next to climate change faced by humans" (World Economic Forum, 2017). This research studies global Cybercrime trends affecting society, business, and government analyzing international legal instruments and research. The author conducted a Comparative Legal Analysis of the Council of Europe's Convention on Cybercrime, aka Budapest Convention and Sri Lanka's Computer Crime Act 24 of 2007, and other international and domestic laws using the Black-letter approach and key informant interviews to collect qualitative data.

When viewed through the lens of empirical evidence, this research found a lack of adequate provisions and clear procedures for collecting, preserving, and presenting electronic evidence and weakness in the international legal corporation in the Sri Lankan legal framework. Further, it lacks the integration of personal data protection, privacy, and human rights. Both the Budapest Convention and Sri Lanka frameworks need to cover cloud computing, cryptocurrency, identity theft, and provide a mechanism for resolving extraterritorial jurisdiction conflict resolution. Sri Lankan legal framework needs to expand to include provisions on child pornography, copyright infringement, spam, defamation, electronic forgery, and fraud essential to address the threats posed by the transient and transnational nature of Cybercrimes. Hence, recommend harmonizing domestic laws to address Cybercrimes to protect society, business, government, and critical infrastructure effectively with a multi-stakeholder approach. The regulation of Internet Governance requires enabling transparency and due diligence provided by the law to ensure national security and stability for enabling open, trusted, equitable and secure Cyberspace with effective legal protection.

Keywords : Budapest Convention, Cybercrime, Law Reform, Sri Lanka legal framework

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.0 Introducing an Effective Cybercrime Regime for Sri Lanka: A Comparative Analysis

1.1 Introduction

"Cybercrime is the greatest threat to every company in the world"

(IBM Digital Nordic, 2015).

"Cyberspace is the complex environment resulting from the interaction of people, software and services on the Internet by means of technology devices and networks connected to it, which does not exist in any physical form" (Hogan and Newton, 2015). The Cambridge dictionary defines Cyberspace as an imaginary area without limits where people meet and discover information. Hence the term, "Cyberspace" describes a virtual global network of computers enabling information flow, storage, and sharing by connected users, which does not have a standard, objective definition, but describes anything associated with the Internet, which "has profoundly shaped our world and has changed our lives in both big and small ways ... a functionality we could never have imagined" (Internet Society, 2017).

Cyberspace is used by 40% of the world population for essential personal, business, and government communications, education, and commerce (Internet World Stats, 2019), has become a critical tool in a digitally-driven society today. About 1.8 billion web sites (Internetlivestats, 2020), gigantic social networks use distributed transnational networks and big databases to hold and transmit vast amounts of valuable information. The Internet of Things (IoT) enables remotely controlling of homes, automobiles, healthcare systems, business, energy, and public services critical to everyday life (Hilt et al., 2017). The growth of hostile uses of Cyberspace is threatening its security and stability (The White House, 2018). The World Economic Forum places the risks of Cyberattacks and Data

Fraud only next to natural disasters (World Economic Forum ed., 2017). British government identifies Cybercrimes stemming from organized crime or terrorism as a tier one national security, public safety, and the economy (Masons, 2010; HM 2010). Cybercrimes harm people by violating human rights by denying access to critical information, infrastructure, and services.

Cybercrime regime (USLegal, 2020; UNODC, 2019b) entails a system of global principles for prevention and prosecution of Cybercrime require the application of international and domestic laws due to cross border infrastructure and transnational activities of Cyberspace (ITU, 2019). The Council of Europe's Convention on Cybercrime, also known as the Budapest Convention ratified by Sri Lanka, is a multilateral binding instrument to harmonize and regulate Cybercrime enabling coordinated international efforts. It provides guidelines for any country developing comprehensive national legislation against Cybercrime and a framework for international cooperation between State Parties to this treaty (Council of Europe, 2004; Fernando, 2016).

This research inquires about the threats of Cybercrimes in public life, business, and government, and discuss the importance of harmonization of local laws and initiatives by analyzing the substantive and procedural provisions, and mutual legal aspects in the Budapest Convention guidelines for developing of national legislation for regulating of Cyberspace to prevent and prosecute Cybercrimes (Council of Europe, 2004; Fernando, 2016). The research emphasizes the need for the application of global principles and international laws in national legislation due to cross border infrastructure and transnational nature of Cybercrimes applicable in introducing an effective Cybercrime Regime for Sri Lanka.

1.2 Research problem

Cybercrimes (Joseph, 2006; Britannica, 2019) are threatening the stability and security of Cyberspace. Politically, economically and culturally motivated Cybercrimes can disrupt social life, critical infrastructure, important processes, and data. The cross-border nature of Cyberspace infrastructure, transnational activities, and gaps in the mutual international corporation is challenging the policy and lawmakers to address Cybercrime issues (ITU, 2012). There is a need for domestic models, initiatives, and laws to prevent Cybercrimes creating tension, controversies, and issues in domestic human rights, business, and diplomatic relations spheres (Council of Europe, 2004). The main reason for these ambiguities is the lack of following global principals, norms, and common guidelines for developing comprehensive national legislation against Cybercrime (European Union, 2013; Council of Europe, 2004). It is argued that the current Sri Lankan law on computer crime is inadequate to deal with the emerging threat of Cybercrime, which negatively impacts society, business, government, national security and stability.

1.3 Research questions

1. What is the definition of Cybercrime and its impact on public life, business, industry, and government services?
2. What is the existing legal framework governing Cybercrimes in Sri Lanka?
3. Are the current legal provisions adequate to deal with the emerging threat of Cybercrime?
4. What lessons can be learned from international experience?
5. What recommendations can be made to improve the legal and policy framework governing Cybercrime in Sri Lanka?

1.4 Objectives

- To define the concept of Cybercrime and its impact on public life, business, industry, and government services?
- To analyze the existing legal framework governing Cybercrime in Sri Lanka.
- To assess the adequacy of the current legal provisions to deal with the emerging threat of Cybercrime.
- To learn lessons from international experience?
- To make recommendations to improve the legal and policy framework governing Cybercrime in Sri Lanka?

1.5 Hypothesis

The absence of an effective Cybercrime Regime creates a negative impact on society, business, and government in Sri Lanka.

1.6 Methodology

The research is conducted as a critical review of the literature, and it is library-based research, which aimed to gain current knowledge, including substantive findings and theoretical and methodological contributions from academic-oriented literature about Cybercrime. The research analyses the Computer Crimes Act, No 24 of 2007, to assess its provisions and procedures and inadequacies to address Cybercrimes in Sri Lanka. The research analyzed the Budapest Convention comparatively to understand how it enables pursuing a common criminal policy for the protection of society against Cybercrimes,

harmonize the domestic criminal substantive provisions in the area of Cybercrimes, to provide domestic criminal procedural law powers necessary for the investigation and prosecution of Cybercrimes committed in electronic form, and provisions for mutual legal aspects of international cooperation to address Cybercrimes.

The research conducts 7 key informant interviews ascertain expert opinion from experts in academic, policymaking, technology, legal, and law enforcement professions to understand different perspectives on the threats of cross border and transnational Cybercrimes activities and legal and social challenges in developing of comprehensive national legislation based on guidelines and framework of the Budapest Convention for harmonizing and the regulation to prevent and prosecute Cybercrimes and enabling international mutual corporations. Finally, the research findings present recommendations for policy and lawmakers for designing an effective Cybercrime regime for Sri Lanka.

The Primary legal sources used for the research include Computer Crimes Act, No. 24 of 2007 of Sri Lanka, Convention on Cybercrime known as Budapest Convention, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), Evidence (Special Provisions) Act, No. 14 of 1995, Electronic Transactions Act, Sri Lanka Telecommunications Act (No. 25 of 1991), No. 19 of 2006 , Sri Lanka Penal Code, Intellectual Property Act, No. 36 Of 2003, The Mutual Assistance in Criminal Matters (Amendment) Act, No. 24 of 2018, , United Nations Convention Against Transnational Organized Crime, UK Computer Misuse Act 1990, United Nations Model Law on Extradition, Data protection in the EU, Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, European Convention on Extradition, *US V Nikita Vladimirovich Kuzmin*, *US V Deniss Calovskis* and *US V Mihai Ionut Paunescu*, *United States v. Ivanov*, *R V Way 2015*. Secondary legal sources were cases of Julian Assange, Edward Snowden, Bangladesh Bank Cyber Heist, Black's Law Dictionary, Yale Law Journal, Tallinn Manual on the International Law, and United Nations Global Program on Cybercrime, United Nations, Developments in the Field of Information and Telecommunications (A/C.1/73/L.27/Rev.1.).

1.7 A Summary of main literature

The main literature used in the research comprised Convention on Cybercrime (Council of Europe, 2001), Computer Crimes Act, No. 24 of 2007 of Sri Lanka, The Impact of the Budapest Cybercrime Convention on Sri Lankan Legal System (Fernando, 2016), The Right to Privacy in the Digital Age (OHCHR, 2018), Status of ICT Laws - We are Incompetent in Dealing with Computer Related Laws (Dailymirror, 2018), Research into Human Rights Protocol Considerations (IETF), Paths to Our Digital Future Internet Society, 2017) Understanding Cybercrime: Phenomena, Challenges, and Legal Response (ITU, 2012), Cybercrime, Evidence, and Territoriality: Issues and Options (Kleijssen and Perri, 2017), A World Of Difference: The Budapest Convention on Cybercrime and the E Challenges of Harmonisation (Clough, 2015), Tallinn Manual on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Warfare (Schmitt et al., 2009), Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime (UNODC, 2013), and General Comment No. 34 Human Rights on the Internet (UNHRC, 2011). This literature provided a comprehensive theoretical foundation, information on international and domestic legal frameworks, issues, controversies, and challenges in regulating Cybercrime in depth. The works of a senior lawyer, Sunil D. B. Abeyrathne, and policymaker Jayantha Fernando have contributed to the discourse on Sri Lanka Cybercrime legal framework. However, several domestic research referred, lacked in-depth technical and legal analysis of contemporary Cybercrime and challenges posed in regulations. The research referred to Foundations of Qualitative Research (Sabharwal, 2007), Methodology of Comparative Legal Research (Hoecke, 2018) and other legal research works for developing research methods and methodology.

1.8 Significance of research

Sri Lanka, a nation emerging in the digital economy, addressing Cybercrimes is critical to public life, business, and government services delivery. The research emphasizes the need to apply global principles and international laws in harmonizing the domestic legal framework to address Cybercrimes. Enhancing

domestic criminal provisions and procedural law powers for the investigation and prosecution of Cybercrimes and enlarging international cooperation to address transnational Cybercrimes is critically needed. The Budapest Convention provides guidelines for developing comprehensive national legislation against Cybercrimes and a framework for international cooperation to design an effective Cybercrime Regime. Therefore, the research findings will be useful to Policymakers, Prosecutors, Defenders, and others engaged in bringing cybercrime offenders to justice and the General public in the discourse of designing an effective Cybercrime Regime for Sri Lanka.

1.9 Limitations

Although Sri Lanka has become a State party to the Budapest Convention in 2015, significant progress has not been made in developing comprehensive national legislation against Cybercrimes. There is also a lack of widespread awareness among the society on the threats of Cybercrimes to emphasize the urgent need for an effective Cybercrime Regime for Sri Lanka. Due to a lack of adequate studies conducted on Cybercrimes legal domain and limited awareness of the international Cybercrime Regime among the stakeholder community, there is a limitation on accessible local literature and data collection for generalization of the research. The Cybercrimes Regime involving technology, legal, business, and human rights disciplines is a challenging research area in creating a theoretical foundation, applying theory in research practices. The data collected for the research are limited to the primary and secondary legal sources, Internet resources, and interviews conducted. The literature review found that very few prior research studies have been done in the domestic context, which needs further development in this research area.

1.10 Dissertation outline

Chapter 1 covers the introduction to the research. The chapter presents a literature review and theoretical background for the research. Chapter 3 explains the research methodology. Chapter 4 presents a discussion and analysis of the research. Chapter 5 provides conclusions and recommendations. Other sections include acknowledgments, references, a summary table of main literature, thematic areas for key informant interviews, and key Informants.

Chapter 2: Literature Review and Theoretical Background

2.1 Introduction

This literature review creates a foundational knowledge in theoretical, technological, and legal aspects of Cybercrime, analyzing what has been investigated to identify relevant data sources, how the key concepts have been defined to demonstrate the author's understanding by providing evidence to evaluate the research and contribute to the field critically (SAGE Publications, 2019). The author reviews the nature of Cybercrimes, their implications and threats on public life, business, and government, international and domestic legal challenges, controversies, issues, suggested solutions, and gaps in understanding global principals, norms, and standard guidelines against Cybercrimes.

2.2 Definition of a legal regime

"Law should govern, " said Aristotle. Laws establish acceptable behavior and standards in a civilized society, enabling dispute resolution by balancing different needs, wants, values, and views of people. The state is obliged to protect the liberties and rights of people with laws (Funk, D., 1972) A legal regime is a system of principles and rules governing a society (USLegal, n.d). Laws are key to promote good governance and prevent abject tyranny, hence a product of political and social arrangements on state-society relations and conflict resolution among citizens (Hurst, 2018).

An effective legal system runs by the Rule of Law, which is the legal principle to govern society instead of arbitrary decisions. The rule of law is primarily established in a country with statutes, secondarily with international Conventions, treaties, declarations, and customs. Joseph Raz identified, laws should be prospective, open and clear; relatively stable; open and accessible to all; non-retroactive; no one should be above the law; independent and adheres to

natural justice; have review powers for courts; and crime prevention agencies should not be allowed to pervert the law (Raz, 1972; Clashfern, 2008), and the powers provided to them should have due diligence in order to protect the liberties and rights of people.

2.3 The Cyberspace

"Cyberspace, " synonymous with the Internet (Duhaime, 2020), has become a ubiquitous and intimate tool shaping the next generation of digital society and economy (Internet Society, 2017) and the most beneficial technological invention made in the society known to us. "Over the last two decades, the Internet and, more broadly, Cyberspace has had a tremendous impact on all society parts. Our daily lives, fundamental rights, social, and economies depend on information and communication technology working seamlessly" (Council of Europe, 2013b).

"Cyberspace refers to the set of links and relationships between objects accessible through a generalized telecommunications network" (ENISA, 2016). "The Internet is a network of networks consisting mostly of privately-operated networks; some networks across national boundaries and many organizations across boundaries. The value of the Internet comes from its open and global nature. "(Internet Society, 2018). The increased use of technology in communication, transport, health, energy, and government services delivery has made Cyberspace data and infrastructure a critical component of sustainable human existence, is "a forum for freedom of expression and exercise of fundamental rights, and empowered people in their quest for democratic and more just societies" (European Union, 2013).

The social and economic progress of the Internet is based on its fundamental properties of openness, innovation, interoperability, collaboration, and competition, hence undermining these properties, will risk all the benefits the Internet brings (Internet Society, 2018). Cyberspace has become an organically evolving concept rather than an actual tangible entity having a legal personality. It is not owned by any person, group, organization, or government, and no one

controls it entirely. The globally accepted idea is that everybody owns Cyberspace (Johnson and Post, 1996). "Globalization is a feature of the Internet, not a bug, and legal systems everywhere should recognize this, not try to 'fix' it. Decisions that exert jurisdiction extraterritoriality should be made in ways that allow the Internet to evolve as an open, globally-connected, secure, and trustworthy technology for everyone (Internet Society, 2018). While Cyberspace has helped to advance in every domain from art, science, economics to zoology. It has challenged the exciting international and domestic laws with technology advancement, requiring legal research on Cyberspace to see through a technology filter. The Internet Governance happens in a multi stakeholder mechanism where Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers (ICANN) states that "no one person, company, organization or government runs the Internet". The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) is a self-organized group of people contributing to Internet technologies' engineering and evolution. (Hoffman, 2006). Known as a "Father of the Internet" (Debategraph, 2020), Vint Cerf states that the "Internet does not require government oversight. What it requires is an operation by the private sector with all other entities" (ICANN, 2020).

2.4 Cybercrime

"The annual cost of Cybercrime to the global economy is more than \$4 billion" - Mark Rutte (A-Z Quotes, 2019). "Computer crime emerged soon after the invention of the first computers, from the late 1940s" (Li, 2017), where the first recorded computer abuse occurred in 1958 (Parker, 1989). Anyone with a motive, a computer, an internet connection, tools can easily commit a Cybercrime offense anonymously or by pretending to be another person. Today "Network and information systems and services play a vital role in society." Their reliability and security are essential to economic and societal activities, particularly to the internal market" (European Union, 2016), facilitating the necessary cross-border movement of goods and people. However, this openness is used as a sword by criminals, where we need to shield innocent people and nations.

Cyberspace's malicious use is threatening its security and stability, where over one million people are becoming victims of Cybercrimes each day (European Union, 2018). An offensive or defensive Cyberattack will damage or destroy objects, a process, or cause injury or death to a person (Schmitt et al., 2013) or denial-of-service that have adverse effects on an individual, society, business, or government using computer viruses, phishing, identity theft, data breaches, ransomware, social engineering, denial of service attacks, financial, or other Cybercrimes. Cybercrime cases require a Judge to hear testimony and evaluate the evidence of how the alleged offender entered the network, what were the tools used; hence a judge without technical expertise may not understand how the crime occurred, making it difficult for him to decide whether a defendant committed it and handing down the sentences to make the "punishment fit the crime" (Shinder and Cross, 2008).

The Internet is used by criminals to perpetrate fraud and as a communications medium of global reach and low cost. Hackers penetrate business networks and destroy data, while terrorists could purposely disrupt the critical infrastructures (GIPI, 2005). Cyberattacks have resulted in immense disturbances to society's functioning, causing the closing of the hospitals, taking electrical grids offline, locking financial networks, making cities standstill, affecting the integrity of democracy, or spreading terror among the civilian population (Jang-Jaccard and Nepal, 2014). The Dark Web (Finklea, 2015; Leuven et al., 2016) is used as a digital marketplace for stolen data, cyber attacks, identity theft, child pornography, and criminal services, etc. where payments are made using Bitcoin-like digital currencies (DeVries, 2016). Criminals to terrorists to state-sponsored spies leverage the dark web to carry out traditional crimes as well as technology-based crimes (Finklea, 2015).

The cybercrime-based illicit economy has created more than \$1.5 trillion in profits in 2018 to become a self-sustaining system (Bromium Inc, 2019). Although the need for action against Cybercrime is urged globally, there is still no universally binding Cybercrime agreement, like the Geneva Conventions, due to the cultural and political differences among countries (Clough, 2015).

2.5 Encryption

Encryption helps people to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and economic value of their communications. However, strong encryption restricts lawful criminal or intelligence investigation for law enforcement. In August 2018, the U.S. Department of Justice (DOJ) sought to compel Facebook to comply with a wiretap to intercept voice calls over Facebook's end-to-end encrypted Messenger app. End-to-end encryption protects communications from being understood by anyone other than the parties to the communication. Anyone intercepting the transmission of encrypted data will see gibberish. However, according to news reports, the court denied DOJ's motion to compel (CIS, 2018) . Encryption has helped the emergence of Cryptocurrencies making money a digital commodity. As of 17th September 2020, the total market capitalization of Cryptocurrencies was approximately 352 billion (coinmarketcap.com).

Cryptocurrencies have revolutionized the global digital markets by creating a free-flowing trading system shifting economic paradigms (DeVries, 2016). However, Cybercriminals have established cryptocurrencies as a tool or for the facilitation of Cybercrimes creating a significant challenge for law enforcement to detect illegal transactions for various Cybercrimes (Reddy and Minnaar, 2018; ZDNet, 2014). As of 2017, around 980,000 Bitcoins have been stolen from cryptocurrency exchanges (Reuters, 2017). OneCoin cryptocurrency, founded by Ruja Ignatova, was one of the biggest Ponzi schemes in history, estimated to have stolen up to \$19.4 billion (BBC, 2019). St. Petersburg's Petrogradsky District Court dismissed Bitcoin theft as a crime since cryptocurrency is not regulated in Russia (Bitcoin, 2020b). Most governments in developing countries have faced a challenge in regulating cryptocurrencies, due to nontaxability, self-governance, decentralized nature, usability in money laundering, and the unwillingness of many institutions to recognize them like hard currency. (Cointelegraph, 2019)

2.6 Electronic evidence

Electronic evidence is any information that is stored or transmitted digitally, treated as secondary evidence (Insa, 2007). "Some judges believe that the precision and objectivity of the electronic evidence make it more reliable; other judges think that the lack of means to verify the authenticity of the electronic evidence makes it more vulnerable and, therefore, less reliable than traditional evidence in general" (Insa, 2007). In general, courts consider electronic data as hearsay and secondary evidence. The admissibility of evidence is used to prove a point, requiring the original document to be produced in court as primary evidence.

Electronic evidence is fragile and can be altered, damaged, or destroyed by improper handling or examination, hence requires special precautions that may be taken to collect this type of evidence properly for avoiding challenges of authentication and verification (Ashcroft et al., 2004; UNODC, 2013). However, most business contracts are exchanged, negotiated, and signed through an email having electronic signatures. Their admissibility in commercial courts has made a paradigm shift in the evidence law, which influences law to treat relevance and reliable electronic data as primary evidence (Insa, 2007). The "Metadata" refers to electronic information about other electronic data, like a "fingerprint." Courts should be aware of their potential probative value. Metadata may reveal the device, identification, source, destination, date, time, duration, type, as well as if the content of the evidence has been manipulated or not., hence digitally signing the evidence embedding content, size, timestamp, and signer using one or more BES, AES, or QES like methods (Connective, 2019) suggested.

A most complicated problem in addressing borderless Cybercrime is collecting the electronic evidence needed for prosecution, where "Judges and prosecutors must handle electronic evidence more and more frequently." (Council of Europe, 2018). Generally, data gathering conflicts with territoriality, jurisdiction, privacy, and human rights issues (Kleijssen and Perri, 2017). European Union's General Data

Protection Regulations (GDPR) requires explicit consent from users to use their data for another purpose or shared with a third party.

Most experts, in general, do not follow a universal procedure for obtaining, preserving, and presenting electronic evidence except in Austria and Romania who use a procedural manual (Insa, 2007) as electronic evidence requires special precautions. A significant problem in electronic evidence is their presence in multiple clouds outside investigating criminal justice authority. Even if the device holding the data is lawfully seized and searched, the data controller could be elsewhere (Kleijssen and Perri, 2017), due to the "transnational nature of Cybercrime, it is highly likely that evidence will be located across various jurisdictions" (Interpol, 2019).

Computer forensics helps identify, extract, document, and preserve electronic evidence stored or transmitted during a crime, are like fingerprints, but invisible, hence require special processing techniques to identify and extract these hidden data to create an evidentiary value (Güney, 2019). It is vital to secure a collection of evidence to guarantee the admissibility, evidential integrity of information. Still, the defense will attack unless due process has been followed provided by law. They also can attack the credibility of evidence jeopardizing the entire case. Thus, proper handling of evidence is one of the most critical issues facing all criminal investigators and digital evidence's intangible nature (Cross and Shinder, 2008).

Traditional search warrants may lack the scope to seize electronic evidence, especially when the data is encrypted. The custodian must agree to disclose the key, as decrypting without the key is too difficult or expensive to be practical (Smith et al., 2004). A study conducted on prosecution issues in digital forensics investigations showed that 24 of the 100 cases had their decisions reversed in the appellate court due to limitation of scope in search and seizure procedures in the warrant, lack of authenticity and reliability of tools used, and not using scientific testing. (Cole et.al, 2015). Hence Cybercrime investigative procedures require a standardization of forensics procedures and define required competencies for law enforcement officers collecting forensic evidence.

2.7 Cybercrimes against individuals

Cybercrimes against individuals directly affect any person or their properties. Social engineering deceives and manipulates people to get valuable information that can later be used for illegal activity. Phishing is a form of social engineering used to trick users into providing their login, password, and other sensitive personal information (APWG, 2013). Cyber harassment is a form of bullying on Cyberspace common among teenagers, including posting threats, sexual remarks, rumors, or victims' personal information. Revenge porn distributes sexually explicit images or videos of individuals with an intent of revenge, common by ex-lovers (Nurse et al., 2018). Cyberstalking is an act of following a person online anonymously and monitoring his or her activities. Women and children being followed by men and pedophiles (Tozdan et al., 2020) have become an issue as it is the beginning of a larger crime.

Cybercrime affects individuals with credibility, financial losses, and privacy. A culprit acquiring an identity of someone easily through hacking of a computer or mobile phone or intercepting communications on the internet (ITU, 2012; Manap, 2015). In 2003, a 72-year-old man was arrested by the FBI on alleged telemarketing fraud involving millions of dollars in the United States, but the police later found out that his identity had been stolen by the real perpetrator and found that he had no connection with his alleged crimes at all. Later the real suspect was arrested in Las Vegas (BBC News, 2003). Criminal stealing information may use names and numbers to create new identities for other criminals to get a passport with their pictures and the victim's name. The original cardholder might remain unaware of this until the debt is so outstanding that the bank contacts the account holder (ITU, 2012). Hacking into someone's phone or social media accounts, the criminals will gain access to personal communications that can be used to blackmail the user. "In 2016, an estimated 26 million persons, or about 10% of all U.S. residents aged 16 or older, reported that they had been victims of identity theft" (Harrell, 2019). Criminals by mobile phone account takeovers have begun to foil authentication processes of social media. In 2019

Capital One Financial Corp. breach exposed 100 million records and the Adobe Creative Cloud breach that exposed 7 million users. In 2017 the most extensive U.S. credit bureau, Equifax Inc., suffered a breach that exposed the personal data of 145 million people, including Social Security numbers (iii.org, 2014). The famous "419" scam (Isacenkova et al., 2013) which made many people to incur financial losses as cross-border cases require exchanges between victim and investigator, and between investigators in the different Member States (Robinson et al., 2011). Cyberstalking or women and children being followed by men and pedophiles on social networks (Tozdan et al., 2020) have become an issue as it is the beginning of a larger crime. The cross-border nature of these organized Cyber crimes has made it extremely difficult to apply existing domestic laws without international mechanisms for mutual legal cooperation (Council of Europe, 2001).

2.8 Cybercrimes against business

"Cybercrime is becoming the greatest threat to every company in the world, and also one of the biggest problems with mankind ...Cybercrime will cost the world over \$6 trillion annually by 2021, up from \$3 trillion in 2015" (Morgan, 2019). Cybercrime costs entail damage, destruction, and theft of data, stolen money, theft of intellectual property, lost productivity, embezzlement, fraud, post-attack disruption to the business functions, forensic investigation, restoration and deletion of hacked data, and systems, and further reputational harm (Morgan, 2019), including legal consequences. In 2018, British Airways faced a fine of £183 million on a data breach affecting 500,000 consumers (BBC, 2019b).

Businesses relying on ICT for their operations today have to incur higher upfront costs for protecting their systems, including testing and monitoring against emerging Cyber threats. Finally the costs are often passed on to the customer through higher prices, affecting the economy. Companies tend to change the way they do business, sometimes shutting down e-business services when they cannot protect their systems against Cyber threats adequately (Alberto Et al., 2017).

Some Cybercrimes on business have political motives, evident from Syrian Electronic Army (SEA), launching several attacks to over 120 pro-western and Syrian opposition websites (Cohen, 2014), Russian hackers Interrupting French TV network TV5 Monde in 2015 (PPAE, 2019), hacktivist group "Anonymous" hacking of PayPal website in 2010, in retaliation for PayPal shutting down payment services to WikiLeaks (BBC, 2013).

Businesses using international cloud services for cost-effectiveness are most vulnerable to Cyber attacks generated from outside their jurisdiction. Most businesses do not report Cyberattacks as it can damage their reputation among customers. Cybercrimes targeting businesses are organized crimes, in most cases involving cross-border actors, making it difficult to seek legal remedies even if the attackers are located.

The Bangladeshi bank heist used the SWIFT system to transfer nearly \$1 Billion to different Sri Lanka and the Philippines accounts. The origin of the attack has been connected to the hacker group Lazarus and North Korea" (Hämäläinen et al., 2017). "The negative implications of [financial] crimes can be far-reaching in economic and other respects. The total amount of money involved with credit card theft is estimated at \$400 million annually, whereas stolen patents and trademarks involve \$250 billion a year (Aldesco, 2002; Baron, 2002). Hence, require an effective technological and legal multilateral international cooperation for developing a set of common standards and principles to address Cybercrimes targeting the business.

2.9 Cybercrimes against Government

American citizen Edward Joseph Snowden, an employee, and subcontractor of CIA, copied and leaked highly classified electronic documents, which revealed numerous global surveillance programs run by the National Security Agency (NSA) with the cooperation of telecommunication companies and European governments (BBC, 2020a) creating a discourse on national security, Cybercrime,

and privacy. The United States Department of Justice brought up charges against Snowden of two counts of violating the Espionage Act of 1917 and government property theft, which was considered a Cybercrime. Later he was accused of breaching nondisclosure agreements signed with the U.S. government, prevailed in a summary judgment on both counts stating, "Intelligence information should protect our nation, not provide personal profit ... This lawsuit will ensure that Edward Snowden receives no monetary benefits from breaching the trust placed in him" (US DOJ, 2019). However, Snowden clarified himself as a whistleblower for the public interest "sparked a much-needed discussion about privacy, national security, IT governance and transparency" (Alhinnawi et al., 2020). The Snowden case is still unresolved and presented a challenge in balancing national security and the right to privacy, including international law on private and public policies on electronic information. The state sovereignty principle defined in UN Charter Article 2, which legitimizes political control to help enhance international security against modern-day Cybercrime, makes states obliged to safeguard the public, business, and government functions.

In 2010, Australian citizen Julian Assange, founder, and editor-in-chief of Wikileaks, was accused of conspiracy to commit computer intrusion when WikiLeaks published sensitive material belonging to the United States government (BBC, 2019e), creating an international discourse on national security, asylum, and extradition related to Cybercrimes. Article 3 of the European Convention on Extradition states, "Extradition shall not be granted if the offense in respect of which it is requested is regarded by the requested Party as a political offense or as an offense connected with a political offense" (Council of Europe, 1957; Rao, 1998). If Assange has acted in the public interest and exercising his freedom of expression, "the British government's decision to extradite Assange to the United States contains a host of violations of international law, basic principles of law and especially human rights" (Küçük, 2019). The case of Julian Assange presents a transnational legal challenge on freedom of expression, state sovereignty, Cybercrime, legal protection, public interest, and extradition (Veçoso, 2019).

Political Cybercrimes have different motives, targets, and tactics to cause broader social, political, and economic implications. They may include hacktivism, Cyberterrorism, Cyber Espionage, and Cyberwarfare, committed by self-motivated individuals, organized groups, and nation-states with certain political goals or agenda (PPAE, 2019). The most common attacks were distributed denial of service attacks, resulting in temporary degradation or loss of service on many commercial and government servers" (Ottis, 2008). Moonlight Maze (1998–2001) is the first known major state-on-state Cyber incident. The Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) said that these Cyberattacks originated from Russia (Vicente, n.d.). In 2007 the Estonia Government faced a Cyberattack campaign lasting 22 days, and Ukraine's power grid was interrupted in 2015. German steel mill in 2014, a group of pro-Palestinian hackers caused the website of Tel Aviv Stock Exchange, El Al Airlines, First International Bank of Israel to crash in 2012, U.S. Office of Personnel Management was attacked and interrupted their functions in 2015 (PPAE, 2019).

In 1998 Tamil Tigers guerilla fighters sent over 800 emails daily, flooding Sri Lankan embassies throughout the world, bearing the message, "We are the Black Internet Tigers, and we are going to disrupt your communications systems", to cause anxiety and fear among embassy staff. In 2009 hackers attacked Israel's Internet structure, which included over five million computers in response to Operation Cast Lead in the Gaza Strip. In 2012. German Parliament became a victim of a Cyberattack that infected 20, 000 machines forcing the entire network to shut down. A ransomware paralyzed a hydroelectric power plant in the United States by infecting its computer systems. (Kleijssen and Perri, 2017). A hacker group named "Tamil Eelam Cyber Force" attacked the Sri Lanka Government and private websites around 18th May, in 2018, 2019, and 2020 consecutively to mark the Tamil Eelam's defeat War in 2009. The key informant in Cyber security stated that " it's not possible to identify the sources as they hide behind proxies".

Cybercrimes shift to a new dimension when nation-states engage in attacking against another State, blurring the line between spies and state spinsored malicious hackers (PPAE, 2019). Symantec uncovered evidence linking North Korea to

attacks on Bangladesh, Vietnam, Ecuador, and Poland (Economic Times, 2017). Stuxnet computer worm aimed to cause substantial damage to Iran's nuclear program, targeted the programmable logic controllers (PLCs) used to automate machine processes, which appeared to have been created by the U.S. National Security Agency, the CIA, and Israeli intelligence (Mcafee, 2019). The U.S. government stated that Forensic evidence points to Cyber espionage of Russian intelligence agencies on Cyberattacks on the Democratic National Committee (DNC) computer network in 2015 and 2016, leading to a data breach of classified information that affected NASA, the Pentagon, military contractors, civilian academics, the Department Of Education, and numerous other American government agencies (New York Times, 2019).

The September 11 attack on the United States gives insights into future Cyber terrorism possibilities where terrorists could infiltrate remotely operated weapons with strategic significance, causing critical systems to collapse to "bring countries to their knees ...by inflicting large scale or lasting damage" (Cohen, 2014). Cyber "Terrorism has become one of the major threats facing both states and the international community" (De Frias, 2012) which is an organized Cybercrime with political objectives, has ability to launch coordinated Cyberattacks that may cause immense disturbances to society's functioning, such as taking electrical grids offline, locking financial networks, and making cities standstill as affecting the integrity of democratic processes (Foltz, 2004).

"Cyberwarfare is an arms race that cannot be won by defense alone. In the end, these attacks will likely continue to proliferate both in numbers and severity" (Shackelford, 2010). We are living in an era with "no defensible borders, in which countries are vulnerable to invasion via information, ideas, people, and materials" (Cohen, 2014), where technology-driven terrorism can take new forms with an individual or a group with the necessary expertise, who might collaborate on secured and anonymous Cyberspace, disproportionate to their size. Such actors have the "potential ability to cause damage completely changing the balance of power by penetrating important security or economic systems in every country in

the world and accessing sensitive information, or even by destroying vital systems" (Cohen, 2014).

Critical infrastructures are vital physical or virtual systems and assets of a country such as energy, food, water, fuel, transport, communications, finance, industry, defense, and governmental and public services sectors. Their improper functioning, incapacity, or destruction would have a debilitating impact on national security and defense, economic security, public health, or safety (European Union, 2013). Without a doubt, Cyberterrorism is becoming more serious every day. There can be a day to target nuclear facilities providing energy or other critical infrastructures, creating potentially disastrous consequences on our way of life (Salinas and Council of Europe, 2016). A key informant in the Internet Governance community revealed that many Cyber terrorism incidents are not made public. Hence the unknown cases could be more than what we know.

The United States' 2010 National Security Strategy cited Cyber threats as "one of the most serious national security, public safety, and economic challenges we face as a nation" (Schmitt, 2013). "Nation-state Cyber Warfare hackers target government agencies, critical infrastructure, and industries known to contain sensitive data or property. Hackers look for any data that will benefit their country's economy and strengthen both key business and military strategies. These attacks can shut down critical national infrastructures like energy, transportation, military contractors, and government operations" (PPAE, 2019).

The Tallinn Manual document on the law governing Cyber Warfare in 2009, developed by an independent International Group of Experts, consisting of distinguished international law practitioners and scholars invited by the NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence (NATO CCD COE) based in Tallinn, Estonia. Their work was based on four Geneva Conventions and protocols, Rome's statute, International Law Applicable to Air and Missile Warfare, Convention of Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), and many other international treaties, declarations, and policies related to Cybercrime (Schmitt, 2013). Their effort resulted in "Tallinn Manual," a non-binding document applying existing

legal norms and International Law to Cyber Warfare. The key drivers were September 11th, 2001, transnational terrorist attack on the United States, massive Cyber operations by 'hacktivists' against Estonia in 2007, and Georgia during its war with the Russian Federation in 2008 (Schmitt, 2013).

Every State faces challenges in the scope and manner of application of international law in the Cyber environment, both in defensive and offensive cyber operations, as current international legal norms emerged when Cyber technology was not on the horizon. As a consequence, Cyber practices quickly out distances the governing legal regime (Schmitt, 2013). In this regard, the International Court of Justice's pronounced that international law on armed conflicts applies to "any use of force, regardless of the weapons employed" (Schmitt, 2013); however, the "unique attributes of networked technology require additional work to clarify how these norms apply and what additional understandings might be necessary to supplement them" (The White House, 2018).

The Tallinn manual explores Cyber activities that 'use of force' in the perspective of an armed conflict between states and armed groups; however, it does not address Cybercrimes in detail as well as does not consider international human rights applicability, and telecommunications law. Therefore it's context is limited to notions of the use of force' and 'armed attack, but does not consider the issue of individual criminal liability under either domestic or international law. However, in designing an effective Cybercrime regime, the Tallinn manual provides guidelines for application of existing international law in Cybercrime and the legal nature of the relationship between States, Cyberinfrastructure, and Cyber operations (Schmitt, 2013).

The surveillance capabilities, tools, financial resources, and expertise at the disposal of nation-states make them highly capable of causing unprecedented damage and disruption. (PPAE, 2019). Cybercrimes with military tactics are attacks on democracy, sovereignty, and national security; Hence, questions domestic and international cybercrime legal instruments are not designed to address nation-state Cybercrimes. Hence politically motivated and nation-state

Cybercrime requires serious consideration for applying the Geneva Conventions on armed conflict, Hague Conventions against the use of weapons of war, and the threat or use of force against "the sovereignty, territorial integrity and political independence of other States" stated in Article 2(4) of UN Charter.

"Every internationally wrongful act of a State entails the international responsibility of that State" (United Nations, 2011). It is challenging to probe Cybercrime to prove attribution due to the high burden of proof required in the doctrine of effective control in cases determined by The International Court of Justice (ICJ). "This problem is magnified in Cyberspace by the speed and anonymity of the Cyber attacks" (Shackelford, 2010), and "distinguishing among the actions of terrorists, criminals, and nation-States is difficult" (The White House, 2018). Russia did not cooperate in the investigation of Cyberattack on Estonia in 2007, which originated from Russian territory. "Given the clandestine nature of Cyberspace, States may thus incite civilian groups within their borders to commit Cyber attacks and then hide behind a, however sheer, veil of plausible deniability and thus escape accountability" (Shackelford, 2010)

Rule 14 of Tallinn Manual states that a State bears international legal responsibility for Cybercrimes. The Responsibility of States for Internationally Wrongful Acts considers the conduct of a person or group of persons shall be considered an act of a State under international law if the person or group of persons is acting on the instructions of, or under the direction or control of, that State in carrying out the conduct (United Nations, 2011). ICJ also has held, in the context of military operations, that the conduct of non-State actors may be attributable to a State for the failure to act having effective control to prevent violation of international law, which could be extended to Cybercrime. This obligation of state responsibility applies to Cyber Operations Launched from or routed through Governmental Cyber Infrastructure and Cyber Operations Routed Through a State Network. Hence the injured State may resort to proportionate countermeasures, including Cyber countermeasures, against the responsible State (United Nations, 2011).

2.10 Human rights in Cyberspace

"Human rights are always bounded, granted, bestowed, enjoyed, received, performed, and violated in real, physical places" (Wagner et al., 2019). Although digital and pseudonymous, interactions on the Cyberspace represent real humans, require adherence to human rights principles, norms, and laws applicable in the physical world for enabling open, trusted, equitable and Secure Cyberspace. RFC 8280 on Developing Human Rights Protocol Considerations states that technology cannot be deduced from the impact on human rights (IETF, 2017) specifically the denial of access to services, data, or websites would infringe rights of "disclosing vital information about malpractice on the part of a government or other authority" (IETF, 2017). "Cybercrime, even if carried out by ordinary criminals or terrorists, poses a grave threat to democracy and our security" (Kleijssen and Perri, 2017).

The increased use of social media has resulted in governments' regulatory responses, including the use of criminal law, and calls for respect for rights to freedom of expression. (UNODC, 2013). However, The socio-cultural element of some limitations is reflected in national laws and multilateral instruments on broad offenses regarding the violation of public morals, pornographic material, and religious or family principles or values (UNODC, 2013). Hence "Laws seeking to balance rights and responsibilities often distinguish between public and private conduct" (AHRC, 2013).

Cyber Crimes against human rights include insults, defamation, fake news, hate speech, obscenity, or pornographic material. On the other hand, government agencies investigating Cybercrime intercepts communications and perform electronic surveillance, which may violate human rights to privacy, free expression, and freedom of association. Hence a balance is required between Cybercrime prevention and human rights (UNODC, 2011; APC, 2019). Any restriction of these rights should be done with a legitimate aim under specific circumstances to protect national security, public order, public health, morals, or protection of others' rights. Such restrictions may be implemented in accordance

with the existing law, and necessary, and proportionate to the threat of the Cybercrime (UNHRC, 2011).

Freedom of expression on the Internet is an important right that facilitates other essential economic, social, cultural, civil, and political rights. The UNHRC resolution A/HRC/RES/32/13 condemns the practice of preventing and disrupting individuals' access to the Internet, stating that "same rights that people have offline must also be protected online, in particular freedom of expression, which is applicable regardless of frontiers and through any media of one's choice" (A/HRC/RES/20/8; A/HRC/RES/38/7; A/RES/68/167; UNODC,2019b). The United Nations General Assembly also recognized "that the exercise of the right to privacy is [also] important for the realization of the right to freedom of expression and to hold opinions without interference, and is one of the foundations of a democratic society" (A/RES/68/167; UNODC,2019b). On March 07, 2018 Government of Sri Lanka (GOSL) blocked Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp and internet access in Kandy district to curb hate speech related to communal riots (LBO, 2018). The blockade continued for 7 days. Following the Easter Sunday Attack, on the 21st of April 2019, GOSL again blocked Social Media for 12 days. These blockades, done arbitrarily, affected the rights to work, freedom of expression, right to association, and right to education of individuals using social media.

Governments globally manipulate internet governance unlawfully, restricting internet freedom with negative regulatory policies and traffic controls through ISPs and communication access points (IXP, submarine cables, satellite connections, optical fiber links) for Internet surveillance, blocking websites, pressing social media companies to remove certain content, including threats and hacking activists. The end-to-end principle (Saltzer et al., 1984) in technologies is critical to keeping the application-specific features accessible only to the end nodes of the communication network; the intermediate nodes only pass data randomly. Net Neutrality at the ISP level prevents payload, source, or destination-based discrimination of packets for keeping the internet free and open (EDRI, 2013).

United Nations Special Rapporteur on the promotion and protection of the right to freedom of opinion and expression states that "certain forms of expression should be prohibited by international law, among them are the advocacy of national, racial or religious hatred that constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility or violence, and direct and public incitement to commit genocide" (UNODC, 2013). This prohibition is also enshrined in Article 20(2) of the ICCPR and Article III(c) of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide of 1948 prohibits direct and public incitement to commit genocide (UNODC,2013). Cybercrimes negatively impacting human rights, democracy, and the rule of law need to be addressed as a serious threat to our society's core values. Hence we need a more secure and resilient digital ecosystem to prevent digital security threats and incidents continuing to grow in number and sophistication, with significant consequences (OECD, 2017) on human rights, requiring cross-border enforceable Cybercrime prevention mechanisms.

2.11 Jurisdiction on cyber activities

The term jurisdiction primarily means a court's power to hear and decide a case or make a certain order within the territory of that State's sovereignty (ECtHR, 2015). The Cyberspace without defined territories raises the question of "which court can exercise jurisdiction over a defendant located or domiciled in a country other than the country in which a complaint has been made" (ECtHR, 2015)? In Cyberspace, the Courts need to establish jurisdiction irrespective of geographic location, on the principle of universality, which is viewed as crimes affecting all human beings (UNODC, 2013).

The Constitution and Convention of the International Telecommunication Union (CS CV) preamble recognize "the sovereign right of each State to regulate its telecommunication" (ITU, 2019), placing a mutual obligation of Member States to prevent Cyber Crimes originated, transmitted via, or moved to their territory. A State may exercise its Jurisdiction over persons engaged in Cyber activities on its territory and Cyberinfrastructure located on its territory, which include authority to

prescribe, enforce, and adjudicate civil, criminal, or administrative matters related to Cybercrime (ITU, 2019). When multiple countries are involved in a Cybercrime investigation, one may be reluctant to act than others or extract the offender for political reasons. The lack of a universal Convention on mutual legal corporation constraints formal search, seizure, data preservation for electronic evidence collection, and extraditions related to transborder Cybercrimes.

2.12 Cybercrime legislation

"The first federally prosecuted computer crime was the alteration of bank records by the computer in Minneapolis in 1966" (Parker, 1989). Computer crimes are correlated to the increase of computers in government, business, and personal domains, and the growth of cross border networks (Schjolberg, 2008). Many nations have tried to apply traditional laws that were not meant for addressing Cybercrimes but failed to keep pace with "endless race" (Abeysekara, 2015) in Cyberspace. Authorities tried to apply vague interpretations of existing laws, instead of creating specific provisions and procedures applicable to Cybercrimes (Li, 2017; Qianyun, 2016).

The emergence of an international Cybercrime regime is a gradual and collaborative process enabled by various government, business, academia, and civil society (OHCHR, 2014). The Ribicoff Bill attempted to define and outlaw computer crimes in 1979. (Taber, 1978). Interpol, addressing computer crime and penal legislation at a conference in Paris in 1979, stated that "the nature of computer crime is international, because of the steadily increasing communications by telephones, satellites" (Schjolberg, 2008), highlighted the transnational nature of Cybercrimes, stressing that legal issues are global.

United States enacted The Computer Fraud and Abuse Act (CFAA) in 1984, prohibiting accessing a computer without due authorization (Marshall et al., 2010; NACDL, 1984), and the United Kingdom promulgated the Computer Misuse Act in 1990, laying the foundation for the criminalization of computer crimes. UN

Manual on the Prevention and Control of Computer-Related Crime in 1994 (United Nations, 1994). The Council of Europe's Recommendation *No. R (95)13* in 1995 providing guiding principles for investigating authorities in the field of information technology, European Parliament adopting a resolution in 1997 on "illegal and harmful content on the Internet, and G-8 Justice and Interior Ministers adopting ten Principles to Combat High-Tech Crime in 1997 (Schjolberg, 2008) created a global discourse and a consensus on the need of an international Cybercrime instrument.

In 1999, The US President established the Electronic Frontier Foundation Group (EFF), enabling civic participation in Cybercrime legal and policy issues to protect civil liberties from unlawful acts by law enforcement (EFF, 2020) In 1999, Stanford University introduced Stanford Draft Convention 2000 on International Cooperation to Combat Cyber Crime and Terrorism ahead of the 9/11 attack on the United States in 2001. In 2000 the United Nations General Assembly adopted resolutions 55/63, 56/121 on "Combating the criminal misuse of information technologies, " calling States to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data and computer systems from unauthorized impairment ensure that criminal abuse is penalized. The Council of Europe, creating a Committee of Experts on Crime in Cyberspace (PC-CY) in 1999, approved the Draft Convention on Cyber Crime created by PC-CY in 2001 (Tafazzoli, 2018).

In 2004, The Council of Europe's Convention on Cybercrime (Budapest Convention), became the first binding international instrument entered into force. The Budapest Convention aimed to address Cybercrimes by harmonizing national laws, improving investigative techniques, and increasing cooperation among nations, became the most significant milestone of developing international Cybercrime norms (Schjolberg, 2008).

The World Summit on the Information Society (WSIS), held in Geneva in 2003, declared a Plan of Action, included an action line C5 for "Building Confidence and Security in the use of ICTs", providing several measures for governments take in cooperation with the private sector, to "prevent, detect and respond to Cyber-crime

and misuse of ICTs" (WSIS, 2003). The WSIS Tunis Agenda for Information Society held in 2005, Created the Internet Governance Forum (IGF), a multi stakeholder governance group including technical and academic community for policy dialogue on issues of Internet governance, and called upon world governments to make legislative reforms "to develop necessary legislation for the investigation and prosecution of Cybercrime" taking into account existing frameworks and regional initiatives "including, but not limited to, the Council of Europe's Convention on Cybercrime" (WSIS, 2005; Clough, 2015).

The International Telecommunication Union (ITU), launching Global Cybersecurity Agenda (GCA) to facilitate action line C5, emphasized that "Internet is an international communication tool and, consequently, any solution to secure it must be sought at the global level" (Clough, 2015), highlighting the need for harmonization of national legislation with a globally applicable and interoperable framework is address transnational Cybercrimes (Schjolberg, 2008; (ITU, 2012). As criminals have found a new lawless environment in Cyberspace for their offenses, it's imperative that Cyberspace needs similar laws across nations, with a Convention enabling a common understanding to help eliminate legal gaps in Cybercrime regulation (ITU, 2012), hence harmonization of legislation in the individual countries creates a possibility to agree on a universal Convention on Cybercrime.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the research method and methodologies used in the research to answer research questions, how the primary and secondary data collected, what tools were used, how the data was analyzed, ethical considerations, limitations in methodology, and problems encountered during the research.

3.2 Research approach

The Cybercrime laws in Sri Lanka is an under-researched topic. Several research works had been conducted on legal perspectives but lacked an integrated technical and legal approach to justify the need for harmonizing with international legal instruments, which is essential to address the technological, transnational, and transient nature of Cybercrimes. Therefore this research tries to marry the technological and legal perspectives for introducing an effective Cybercrime regime for Sri Lanka.

3.3 Research methods

This research mainly used the qualitative research strategy (Sabharwal, 2007), including some quantitative aspects using data obtained through literature. The research was primarily grounded on the "Comparative Legal Analysis" (Eser, 1997; Hoecke, 2018). This methodology tries to study the differences, similarities, and interrelationships between different legal systems for reforming the domestic legislative framework to face emerging legal challenges (Legrand, 1995). The importance of Comparative legal analysis methodology has been recognized enormously globally in harmonizing domestic law in cultural integration, internationalization, economic globalization, and democratization (Picker, 2013).

The author found Comparative Legal Analysis as a practical approach for learning and a better understanding of legal knowledge elsewhere, as well as local perspectives as it provides an evolutionary and taxonomy of common evolutions, diachronic changes, and legal families, and contributes to deeper understanding and improving one's legal system for harmonization of domestic law (Smits, 2014; Hoecke, 2018).

The methods included reviewing the Tallinn manual to understand Cybercrime regarding the Geneva Conventions' existing legal framework and their applicability as international legal instruments, and the author answers the research questions by viewing Sri Lanka Computer Crime Act No 24 of 2007 (CCA) through the Budapest Convention's lens, comparing and contrasting, and finally applying perspectives of key informants to make recommendations for harmonizing domestic law. When comparing the Budapest convention and Computer Crimes Act 27 of 2007, the research followed the "Black letter" methodology concentrating solely on the "letter of the law" (Qureshi, 2015), which insists that law is a pure concept, independent of morality, politics/power or other outer influences (Chynoweth, 2009). However, the author was compelled to consider sociological roles played by public policy on Internet Governance to offer commentary for legal reforms. For this purpose, the author applied Constructivism, which is "an approach to learning that holds that people actively construct or make their own knowledge and the learner determines that reality" (Elliott et al., 2000) for interpreting the information obtained from key informant interviews in the discussion. The author also sought input from senior professionals in the field and conducted informal discussions with personal contacts to understand the key concepts, issues, and Cybercrime legislation challenges in Sri Lanka. However, constructivists believe that foreign law in the National legal system can create resistance from protected culture and legal tradition (Brunnée and Toope, 2018).

3.3 Research design

For this research, the author developed an essential literature list and conducted a comprehensive literature review to improve the understanding of the nature of Cybercrime and related legal and technical issues. The review focused on assessing the impact of Cybercrime from social, business, and government perspectives to evaluate the legal challenges posed by the transnational nature of Cyberspace. Conducting key informant interviews helped to obtain professional perspectives on thematic areas. Finally, international and domestic legal provisions and procedures were analyzed to assess the fundamental changes required to harmonize domestic law enforcement approaches, evidence gathering, including international cooperation mechanisms in criminal matters.

3.4 Sources

The content presented in this research comes from a wide range of sources apart from interviews and references related to Cybercrime. The Primary legal sources used for the research include Computer Crimes Act, No. 24 of 2007 of Sri Lanka, Convention on Cybercrime known as Budapest Convention, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), Evidence (Special Provisions) Act, No. 14 of 1995, Electronic Transactions Act, and Sri Lanka Penal Code including local and international legal instruments. Secondary legal sources were cases of Julian Assange, Edward Snowden, Bangladesh Bank Cyber Heist, Hacking of Sri Lanka President's Website. Black's Law Dictionary, Yale Law Journal, Tallinn Manual on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Warfare and United Nations Global Program on Cybercrime, United Nations, Developments in the Field of Information and Telecommunications in the Context of International Security (A/C.1/73/L.27/Rev.1.), including legal research papers, books, and other publications collected through on-line searches publicly available on the internet for the analysis. This approach helped research to create an overall comparative global perspective on the status of Cybercrime regimes and frameworks; criminalization of Cybercrime; Cybercrime law enforcement and investigations;

electronic evidence and criminal justice; international cooperation in criminal matters involving Cybercrime; and measures for prevention of Cybercrime (UNODC, 2013).

3.5 Instrument Design

The author designed 10 thematic areas to interview key informants (Winchester, 1999), to reflect their knowledge, experience, and opinions. The main aim was to obtain their understanding of Cybercrime, Budapest Convention, Computer Crimes Act, Assess the advantages of the Budapest Convention and its international applications including case law development, learn about gaps in Sri Lanka Cybercrime legislation, trends, and their recommendations for harmonizing Sri Lanka Cybercrime legislations. The Questions and interview notes have been attached to the appendixes.

3.6 Key informant interviews

The primary data were obtained from key informants representing Legal Academia, Legal Practice, Internet Governance and Community, Technology, Policy, and Judiciary fields related to Cyberspace and Cybercrime legislation. Formal discussions were held with them based on structured questions, mixed with open discussions, and recorded responses. Key informants interviewed were experts with knowledge of the research problem and related themes. They were helpful in the interpretation of the literature review findings. They provided legal, technological, and social perspectives on the research phenomenon, contributed to expanding and understanding insights created by the research, and helped reduce potential bias (Cossham and Johanson, 2019).

3.7 Results

The outcome of this comparative analysis was aimed to provide insights into how the Sri Lanka Cybercrime regime could be designed to fill gaps in existing legislative provisions and procedures to address Cybercrimes effectively. The author found key differences and similarities, and interrelationships in these instruments. The Budapest Convention is a binding legal instrument and framework, providing guidelines for harmonizing the domestic law. The CCA is applicable legislation of National law. However, they both provide similar substantive provisions, but CCA provides limited investigative procedures. CCA has a gap in International corporation. The Budapest Convention is comprehensive in language and coverage, hence adaptable globally, while CCA lacked essential electronic evidence and protection of human rights procedures. Both instruments lacked privacy and data protection procedures.

3.8 Ethical considerations

There were several ethical issues taken into consideration in this research. Obtaining informed consent from the participants was important. All of the participants were informed in advance about this project's purposes, and their identity and the names of the organizations they belong to have been kept confidential, thus meeting the requirements of the code of ethics of the University of Colombo.

3.9 Problems and limitations

The research encountered several problems and challenges, including time and cost, including the researcher's legal academic field experience. The research would have included more key informants from law enforcement and legal policy to increase multiple perspectives.

Chapter 4: Discussion and Analysis

4.1 Summary of key findings

"Crime is just as much a threat online as it is offline" - Thorbjorn Jagland, (Council of Europe, 2011). Cybercrime is evolving as a sophisticated threat to society, business, and government, where "no other type of crime can become transnational so effortlessly" (Clough, 2010). the gaps in domestic laws (ITU, 2012) to establish a "universal Jurisdiction over perpetrators" (Stahl, 2011). Sri Lanka enacted the Computer Crimes Act in 2007 and ratified the Budapest Convention providing a universal framework and guidelines for developing national legislation with the international corporation for addressing transnational Cybercrimes (Council of Europe, 2004) in 2015. The impact of the Budapest Convention is by May 2020, 76 States (39%) were either Parties (65 States) or Signatories to the Convention, and 177 States (92%) worldwide were in the process of reforming their legislation or had done so in recent years. (Council of Europe, 2020b)

The Computer Crime Act, no. 24 of 2007 of Sri Lanka (CCA) is inadequate (Tarindu, 2020; Walpita, 2019; Thananchayan, 2019) and requires "a lot of tightening up and editing of the provisions of the Act has to be attended to" (Selvakkumaran, 2008), to deal with emerging threats of Cybercrimes.

This discussion analyses the Sri Lankan Cybercrime Regime through the lens of the Budapest Convention for identifying similarities, interrelationships, differences, and gaps to gain insights for harmonizing the domestic legislative framework (Legrand, 1995).

The Budapest Convention aimed to protect society against Cybercrime (Council of Europe, 2005), while CCA provides provisions for identifying computer crimes and procedures to investigate such crimes. Hence the Budapest Convention is broader and comprehensive in scope. The judiciary's key informant revealed that

CCA's limitations might be due to a lack of law enforcement resources for investigating Cybercrimes. Although CCA provides extraterritorial jurisdiction provisions, it lacks procedures for achieving international cooperation to collect transnational electronic evidence.

In the *García Ruiz v. Spain* case, ECtHR declared that "electronic evidence should be neither discriminated against nor privileged over other types of evidence." Therefore, courts need to adopt a neutral approach to technology, which means any technology that proves the authenticity, accuracy, and integrity of data should be accepted. According to the key informant in Judiciary Electronic Transactions Act, No. 19 Of 2006 (DSROSL, 2006) and Evidence (Special Provisions) Act (No. 14 of 1995) (DSROSL, 1995a), should be considered together with CCA. However, the Evidence (Special Provisions) Act focuses on admissibility and not on discovery (Marsoof, n.d.) required to retrieve deleted data using computer forensics. ECtHR stated in *Letinčić v. Croatia* case, "a party should not be deprived of the possibility to challenge the authenticity of electronic evidence ... party should not be deprived of the opportunity to submit relevant metadata to prove the reliability of the printout" (Council of Europe, 2019). In cases *Koger Inc. & Koger (Dublin) Ltd v. O'Donnell & Others*, *Sretaw v. Craven House Capital PLC*, and *Gallagher v. RTE*, courts have considered Metadata as important for authenticating the provenance of electronically created documents. A key informant in legal practice pointed out a lack of procedure to address the transient nature and metadata of electronic evidence as a CCA gap.

In general, the key informants agreed that CCA lacks procedures for enabling mutual international legal corporation for evidence collection and extradition. The European Union's GDPR places restrictions on raw biometric data processing, such as a natural person's physical, physiological, or behavioral characteristics. Although the 1978 Constitution Sri Lanka does not explicitly recognize the right to personal privacy, the Supreme Court of Sri Lanka has highlighted the importance of the individual's right to privacy in *Hewamanna v Attorney General* (1994) and *Sinha Ratnatunga v. The State* (2000) (WorldLII, 2006; OTDG, 2019) A key informant in Internet governance pointed out the lack of human rights and privacy

considerations in CCA. The Budapest Convention also "needs substantial improvement in order to protect the rights of the users whose data will be disclosed under it" (CDT, 2019).

Both The Budapest Convention and CCA do not include explicit provisions and procedures for protecting Critical Infrastructure against Cybercrimes (Baron, 2002), which are not primarily designed to be in Cyberspace (ENISA, 2016). Considering the challenges Sri Lanka faces in recent history from Terrorism, new National policies and laws are required to protect critical infrastructures accessible through Cyberspace (CISA, 2019; CISA, 2020). The research also found a lack of procedure to assert the degree of criminality and proportionality of the punishment, which is an important aspect of asserting damages.

In general, the CCA lacks standardized procedures on electronic evidence collection, preservation, authentication, presentation, and archival, which challenges their admissibility, originality, and weight, stated key informants in the judiciary and legal practice. The key informants suggested the need for new legislation covering the transient nature of electronic evidence, social media abuse, spam, phishing, internet of things, cloud computing, cryptocurrencies, electronic forgery and fraud, identity theft, Cyber harassment, Cyberstalking, child pornography, and electronic deformation. Although Sri Lanka ratified the Budapest Convention, enacting and incorporation required for application within domestic legislation, which is a dualist system (Clough, 2015)

4.2 Definitions

Both The Budapest Convention and CCA do not explicitly reference Cybercrime or the internet, which "is a global computer network through which the almost-instant delivery of data or files occurs between connected computers" (Duhaime, 2020). However, the terms "data, web, commercial, accessible, communication, idea, telecommunications, virtual" also describe the Internet.

A key informant in Academia described Cybercrime as a computer crime component, requiring a connection through a network. CCA legislators using the term "computer crime" thinking that it was synonymous with "Cybercrime" (Fernando, 2016), has created a gap in criminalizing specific wrongful acts in Cyberspace such as spam, Cyberstalking, Cyber harassment, hate speech, copyright infringement, phishing, and identity theft.

Both the Budapest Convention and CCA definitions do not explicitly include smart mobile devices with information processing and internet access capabilities, with a variety of chips and sensors such as GPS, gyroscope, microphone, camera, and accelerometer as essential building blocks of ICT infrastructure (Guelzim et al., 2016), hence restricts access to GPS logs like data of a criminal.

The UK computer misuse act had left definitions to the Courts. In *the DPP v McKeown*, *DPP v Jones* cases, Lord Hoffman defined a computer as "a device for storing, processing and retrieving information" (CPS, 2019a). However, effective Cybercrime legislation requires consideration of various types of new computing devices, programs, data, networks, engineering, sciences, interconnectedness, communications, remoteness, processing, sensing, controlling, and performing various functionalities operations related to electronics, engineering, and scientific disciplines. As an example, a "Computer" can represent any device, equipment, or facility which uses a computer program or other methods of instructions, stored either temporarily or permanently, to perform specific functions with or without data or a program that can store, retrieve, alter, transmit or communicate the results of the operations to a person, computer program, computer, a computer system, or computer network (KLRC, 2012). Such definition would encompass the internet of things, cloud servers, biological, nanotechnology, wearable devices, to perform a specific function or functions (KLRC, 2002) to commit crimes against a whole system or use an entire system such as a botnet (Trendmicro, 2020) to attack an extraterrestrial system.

The definition of "Computer software" needs to encompass computer programs as well as operating procedures, designs, and technical documentation for the

operation of a computer, computer system, or computer network for control of a system or processing of data (KLRC, 2002), further apply to operating systems, desktop applications, drivers, network tools, testing tools, firewalls, antivirus, scripts, agents, bots inter alia.

The definition of "Data" requires a broader representation to include formal or informal data, including raw data or information, knowledge, facts, concepts, or instructions stored or intended to be stored or processed, or is being stored or processed, or has been stored or processed, in a computer, computer system, or computer network (KLRC, 2002) representing the transient nature of data.

The definition of "Computer network" needs to include modems, bridges, routers, switches, repeaters, antennas, towers, wireless devices or satellites connected by hardwiring, cables, communications lines (KLRC, 2002), including Molecular Networks enabling the biological cell to cell communication (Fuxe et al., 2009), and Body Area Networks that place wireless sensors over or inside the body of a patient, to collect biomedical data (Mukherjee et al., 2019) that may be subject to future legal conflicts.

CCA considers "service provider" as an entity that provides connectivity for communication or data services for users. However, the internet's advancement has enlarged the service providers to various services governed by a service agreement, including hardware, consulting, legal, financial, communications, storage, and processing.

Having a comprehensive set of definitions allows effective application of substantive provisions and investigation procedures against Cybercrimes evolving with changing technology. Clear explanations help law enforcement perceive threats quickly, evaluate the damage, collect supporting evidence for the prosecution, and help determine the degree of crime, enabling Judiciary to hand over the most appropriate punishment to criminals (KLRC, 2002; McEwen, 1988).

4.3 Intention to commit an offense

In criminal legislation, the mental element, or *Mens Rea*, the subjective state of mind, must accompany an act to constitute an offense (LII, 2017). The Budapest Convention Article 2 on illegal access and article 5 on unauthorized modification stresses the mental element of intention (without right or authorization) to constitute prescribed offenses to be identified as a crime (Selvakkumaran, 2008). In CCA, section 4 (b) 1 states that "mere turning on of a computer is sufficient" to constitute an offense of illegal access, is questionable as an accidental turning on a computer is not sufficient to establish the constituent element of intention in Section 3 and 4 (Selvakkumaran, 2008).

A port scan (De Vivo et al., 1999) is used to inspect a server's vulnerabilities. Hackers use port scanning to find a weak point on a target host and launch attacks on an open port. Port scanning is considered a "trial of intrusion" rather than "intrusion." This action is beyond "lawful authority" and is based on "dishonest intent" (Oh and Lee, 2014). If the perpetrator was not prohibited but caught while port scanning, how would law enforcement prove the intentional component as no real crime has been committed? "Port scanning is subject to punishment in Korea because it is regarded as an attempt to attack" (Oh and Lee, 2014).

Cybercrimes are also caused by recklessness, negligence, and carelessness resulting from unreasonable standards of conduct that represent varying degrees of blameworthiness or culpability to deserve punishment (Eugene, 1939). This clause highly relevant to the protection of Critical Infrastructure (CISA, 2019) has been left out in both the Budapest Convention and CCA.

4.4 Substantive provisions

Substantive provisions are the "law that creates or defines rights, duties, obligations, and causes of action that can be enforced by law" (Merriam-webster, 2020).

4.4.1 Data and systems

Data theft was a rapidly growing threat in the Cyberspace. In 2019, 4.1 billion records of personal data were stolen among 3800 reported data breaches, which is a 54% increase from 2018 (Norton, 2019). Although the Budapest convention is strengthened with the European Union's GDPR, the Sri Lankan Cybercrime Regime does not include data protection provisions and procedures.

Budapest Convention criminalizes the illegal interception in Article 3, and Article 20 and 21 empower competent authorities to intercept, collect or record traffic data and content data, subject to the protection of human rights, with judicial supervision. CCA Section 8 criminalizes traffic data interception without lawful authority protecting eavesdropping; however, it does not include content data. Section 18 (1) of CCA empowers law enforcement authority to obtain "any information including subscriber information and traffic data" on a warrant issued by a Magistrate. However, Article 18 (2) enables law enforcement authorities to intercept data without a Warrant on an urgent basis, as well as stating "any information" may be misinterpreted as "content data," creating a possibility for violating the right to privacy and freedom of expression. CCA's major weakness is the lack of ensuring human rights with judicial supervision stressed in the Budapest Convention.

The data is only valuable when they are accurate, trustworthy, and has not been unlawfully modified. Data Interference affects data integrity. US Intelligence

chiefs accused Russia of interfering in the 2016 election, is an alarm ringing on democracy of the world (BBC, 2020b).

Article 4 of the Budapest Convention criminalizes the data interference with intentional damaging, deletion, deterioration, alteration, or computer data suppression without rights. The CCA Section 5 harmonizes data interference, expanding it to the unauthorized use of computer time and introducing of malicious computer programs, however, does not relate to privacy rights provided in ICCPR Article 17, which states, "No one shall be subjected to arbitrary or unlawful interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to unlawful attacks on his honor and reputation".

The 'LoveBug' computer virus, released by a student in the Philippines, caused worldwide loss between US\$6.7 billion to US\$15.3 billion in computer downtime; however, the prosecution failed due to the absence of appropriate legislation (Grossman, 2000). Article 5 of the Budapest Convention criminalizes the system interference protecting computers and networks against attacks. CCA lacks an explicit provision against system interference, which is a significant weakness in protecting network-based devices, cloud servers, the Internet of things, and critical infrastructures. Section 6 of CCA protects the national security, national economy, and public order from computer crimes; however, it lacks procedures for developing the prompt capability to respond to attacks, investigate intrusion events, collect, and disseminate attack profiles and warnings (Goodman et al., 2003).

4.4.2 Misuse of devices

The Budapest Convention Article 6 criminalizes the misuse of devices to commit prescribed offenses. The Convention allows authorized tools for testing and protecting computer systems, which hackers can use to commit an offense. As Cyber-attacks are conducted anonymously within minutes, when traces are deleted, it makes it hard for law enforcement to track criminals in real-time. Security professionals performing routine security testing and automatic data

collection have concerns over this provision that may allow a nation to outlaw security testing and security tools (Baron, 2002). Sri Lanka has reserved the right not to apply Article 6 (1), with the exception of paragraph 1(a)(ii) related to computer password, access code, or similar data capable of unlawful access to a computer system. Section 9 of CCA criminalizes using illegal devices (a computer, program, password, or access code) capable of accessing a computer unlawfully with the intent to commit a prescribed offense. Hence mere keeping such tools in possession for security testing and educational purposes will not constitute an offense.

4.4.3 Corporate liability

The Budapest Convention Article 12 on Corporate liability establishes the criminal, civil, or administrative corporate liabilities of Cybercrimes committed by any natural person acting under the authority and exercising control for the organ's benefit. CCA Section 1 defines a "person" as a body of persons, corporate or unincorporated, placing responsibility for the offense on organization management. CCA Section 30 holds a body of persons, including every director and every officer responsible for management and control, to be guilty of an offense committed unless they can prove that they have exercised all due diligence to prevent such offense. This provision places an obligation on organizations to establish due diligence and internal procedures to monitor their staff's actions to mitigate potential risks of Cybercrime.

4.4.4 Computer-related forgery and fraud

"Forgery involves a false document, signature, or other imitation of an object of value used with the intent to deceive another" (FindLaw, 2017b), which requires safeguarding electronic documents' authenticity. Electronic documents are made legal under Sri Lanka's Electronic Transactions Act, No. 19 of 2006. Computers, color scanners, graphics software, and high-resolution color printers enable the production of personal, government, and business documents, Counterfeit checks,

invoices, and passports inter alia, which are difficult to detect for the untrained eye (FindLaw, 2017b).

The Budapest Convention Article 7 criminalizes computer-related forgery to result in inauthentic data for legal purposes as if it were authentic. Neither CCA nor Sri Lanka Electronic Transactions Act has an explicit reference to Computer-related forgery. Fraud is a criminal and civil offense; used to deceive someone intentionally for monetary or personal gain. Fraud must be proved "beyond a reasonable doubt". with hard evidence. Common Cyber frauds include identity theft, e-commerce fraud, credit card fraud, and telemarketing fraud (FindLaw, 2017a). The number of reported social media related incidents in Sri Lanka increased from 80 incidents in 2010 to 3685 in 2017 (SLCert, 2018a). among them are Identity theft, fake accounts, photo abuse, phishing, copyright violations, and defamation, a key informant in the Cybersecurity policy revealed. Fake news has an injurious effect on society and causes serious harm for businesses with negative publicity. A fake email distribution stating that a chief executive had resigned the company's stock to fall nearly US\$61, resulting in a loss of US\$110 million to investors and US\$2.2 billion in lost market capitalization. The accused profited more than US\$240, 000, was disgorgement of all the profits, and interest of US\$353, 000, and a civil penalty of US\$102, 642 (Smith et al., 2004). The CCA does not have an explicit provision for addressing Computer-related fraud. Courts treat a "breach of trust" as an aggravating factor for major fraud. A financial consultant to an Australian government transferred out \$8.725 million electronically using another person's name and password, sentenced to seven years and six months (Smith et al., 2004). Recent research finds that certain Cybercriminals are earning around \$2m and others between \$40k to \$1million annually; hence Cybercrime should be linked with money laundering, and the Cybercrime investigative powers should expand to the collection of criminal asset evidence (Anderson et al., 2019) .

4.4.5 Child pornography

Child pornography is "representation, by whatever means, of a child engaged in real or simulated explicit sexual activities" (OHCHR, 2013), which may include live performances, photographs, motion pictures, video recordings, and the recording or broadcasting of digital images (UNICEF, 2020). U.S. Department of Justice states that juvenile victims identified in pornography crimes, 62 percent were female, 25 percent were members of the offender's family, 59 percent were 12–17 years old, 28 percent were 6–11 years old, and 13 percent were less than six years old (US DOJ, 2004).

Sri Lanka ratified the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) in 1991 and the Optional Protocol to the Convention on Rights of the Child (OPSC) on the sale of child prostitution and child pornography. Article 3 of the OPSC requires State parties to criminalize "producing, distributing, disseminating, importing, exporting, offering, selling or possessing for the above purposes child pornography" (OHCHR, 2013). Hence the Sri Lanka government is obliged to protect children from all forms of sexual exploitation.

The Budapest Convention Article 9 criminalizes producing, distribution, offering, transmitting, possessing, and procuring child pornography through a computer system. Sri Lanka has reserved the right not to apply sub-paragraphs sub-paragraph 2(b) "a person appearing to be a minor engaged in sexually explicit conduct," and (c) "realistic images representing a minor engaged in sexually explicit conduct" of Article 9 (Council of Europe, 2020a). The CCA does not include a provision for criminalizing child pornography. The Penal Code (Amendment) Act (No. 22 of 1995) - Sect 8, criminalizes any form of sexually abusing, participation in sexual activity, obscene or indecent exhibition or show for print or other media involving a child (DSROSL, 1995b). However, the key informant in Judiciary stated that this provision is not applicable in Cyberspace's electronic content. Hence, to protect the rights of children, criminalizing Child pornography in Cyberspace is urgently required.

4.4.6 Infringement of copyrights

The Budapest Convention Article 10 criminalizes offenses related to infringements of copyrights based on States' obligations under the Paris Act of 24 July 1971, Berne Convention for Copyright, and the WIPO Copyright Treaty. In Cyberspace, any material can be copied easily, and it is hard for the original creator to prove copyright to deter plagiarism. Peer-to-peer sharing across borders enabled by bit torrents and over the top messengers is a legal challenge in Cyberspace. The CCA has no explicit reference to infringements of copyrights. The Intellectual Property Act, No 36 of 2003, protects intellectual properties by criminalizing the making available to the public by means of an electronic system ... [without] the consent of the owner of the copyright" (DSROSL, 2003). However, the scope of the terms "work" and "electronic system" are not clear to apply to the complexity of intellectual property rights in Cyberspace.

4.5 Investigative procedures

The investigative procedures are laws that provide powers to law enforcement authorities to investigate crimes with search and seizure, gather evidence, analysis, identify, arrest and charge of a suspect, and prosecution (Britannica,2020b).

The Budapest Convention Article 14 provides powers for law enforcement to collect evidence in the electronic form. The CCA has not made a limitation of scope on collecting evidence. It defines "document" as an electronic record, and Articles 6 (2), 14(3), 18(2), 26 (1), 35(2) refers to the term "evidence", but does not include a procedure on "collection of evidence in the electronic form" which is a weakness in the Sri Lankan legislation stated by the key informants.

4.5.1 Expedited preservation of data

Budapest Convention Article 16 and 17 provides a procedure to order a custodian for expeditious preservation of computer or traffic data vulnerable to loss or modification for a maximum period of ninety (90) days (subsequently renewable) to enable investigation. CCA Section 19 empowers an officer to notify the custodian to preserve the information for a maximum of seven (07) days, which could be extended to ninety (90) days on an application made to a Magistrate having jurisdiction.

4.5.2 Expeditious preservation of sufficient data

In Cyberspace, communication happens by transferring small pieces of data chunks or packets across various networks. The packets will be sent across various network paths from the source and get assembled at the destination. (AVI Networks, 2020) Therefore multiple service providers are involved in the transmission. In case data stored in a cloud database, more data service providers will be involved in the process. Budapest Convention Article 17 requires the preservation of sufficient traffic data regardless of whether one or more service providers were involved in transmitting that path of communication. CCA scope of data preservation does not cover extraterritoriality and multiple service providers engaged in a transmission.

4.5.3 Production order

The Budapest Convention Article 18 empowers competent authorities to make a production order to a person, to submit specified computer data, or a service provider to provide subscriber information other than content data to help establish the type of communication and the subscriber information. The CCA Sections 17(4)(c), 18 (1)(i), 18(4) empowers a competent officer to request to disclose,

obtain, intercept or retention of any information or traffic data from a custodian, however lacks extraterritorial applicability, the inclusion of multiple service providers on procedures provided by law.

4.5.4 Search and seizure

The Budapest Convention Article 19 empowers competent authorities to search, access a computer system, seize or secure and retain a copy of data while maintaining data integrity based on a lawful procedure provided by law. CCA Section 18 empowering police officers to search and seize "any information" without a warrant conflict with freedom of expression and privacy. It is also a question of how seized data is protected from a data breach due to vulnerable storage facilities.

4.5.5 Real-time traffic data collection

The Budapest Convention Article 20 empowers competent authorities for real-time collection of traffic data and obliges the service provider to keep the confidentiality of the execution. These powers are subject to a lawful procedure and protection of human rights on the principle of proportionality. CCA does not include a procedure for real-time data collection or refers to the Telecommunications Regulatory Commission, which has sole authority to specify technical standards and procedures for the provision of telecommunication services and ensure compliance by operators with international or other obligations in relation to telecommunications (DSROSL, 1991). The interception of content data is sensitive to human rights issues, which should be provided by law on the principle of proportionality.

4.5.6 Jurisdiction

Cybercrime jurisdiction challenges include the nationality of the offender (principle of nationality; active personality principle), the nationality of the victim (principle of nationality; passive personality principle), the impacts on the interests and security of the state (protective principle), and the state exercising jurisdiction (UNODC, 2013). In 2001, A Russian Court determined that they were competent to hear the *Premininy v. Russia* case when two hackers in Russia hacked a "Green Point Bank" in America. No one challenged the Turkish Criminal Court's competence to block access to a Google Site in the *Ahmet Yildirim v. Turkey* case. In the *Perrin v. United Kingdom* case, the ECtHR declared that the application was manifestly ill-founded, where the convicted French National who was living in the United Kingdom for publishing an obscene article on a website in the USA. In the *United States v. Ivanov* case, Alexey Ivanov was indicted for conspiracy, computer fraud, extortion, and possession of illegal access devices against American businesses and infrastructure under the Computer Fraud and Abuse Act (CFAA), sentenced to 36 months in prison, and ordered to pay restitution of nearly \$700,000 (UNODC, 2019f).

The Budapest Convention Article 22 establishes the jurisdiction for prescribed offenses committed in State's territory, onboard a ship flying State's flag, or onboard an aircraft registered under the State or by State's nationals. However, Each Party reserves the right to the application of domestic law. The Convention does not provide clear criteria for settlement of jurisdictional conflicts when more than one Party claims jurisdiction; They are to consult to determine the most appropriate jurisdiction.

Under the CCA, jurisdiction to hear, try, and determine prescribed offenses is vested with the provincial High Courts, or High Court holden at Colombo for extraterritorial cases. Colombo High Court can request international service providers to produce certain data as Google.com and facebook.com both "comply with a request of a judicial or administrative authority, law enforcement or a

government agency" (Facebook, 2020), where google "send an email to the user account before disclosing information" (Google, 2020). The CCA, applicable to persons, computer systems, and data in or outside Sri Lanka, provides extraterritorial jurisdiction provisions for prosecution of Cybercrimes but lacks clear procedures for the international legal corporation.

4.6 International cooperation

International cooperation enabled by the Budapest Convention aimed to effectively address transnational Cybercrimes, for not allowing any safe havens for criminals. When a State makes a data request to investigate a Cybercrime, the custodian and lawful authority for data may reside in multiple territories of the user, offender, server, and service provider in the cloud computing environment. Therefore, the mutual legal corporation is an essential element in determining jurisdiction in Cyberspace (UNODC, 2015). Article 23 in the Budapest Convention provides general principles for international cooperation on criminal matters and evidence collection.

The Budapest Convention Article 25 requires parties to provide the widest extent of mutual assistance possible for investigations of prescribed offenses, setting out communications, urgent circumstances, security, and authentication levels subject to the conditions of domestic law or applicable mutual assistance treaties. Dual criminality may be waived if the conduct underlying an MLA request is "of a serious nature" (OECD, 2007).

CCA not having explicit international cooperation procedures, hence unable to apply the provisions effectively for extraterritorial offenses stipulated in Section 2. However, the Mutual Assistance in Criminal Matters (Amendment) Act, No. 24 of 2018 (MACMA) Article 4 (1) provides provisions for international cooperation and assistance for locating suspects, obtaining the evidence, search and seizure, expedited preservation of computer data, or traffic data, tracing of crimes

committed via internet, ICT, cloud computing (DSROSL, 2018) with Commonwealth countries, applicable together with CCA.

The Budapest Convention Article 24 provides a procedure for the extradition of criminals who committed offenses established in the Convention. CCA Section 27 amends Extradition Law, No. 8 of 1977 by including the text "(49) An offense committed in terms of the Computer Crimes Act, No. 24 of 2007", empowers the Minister to notify the Government of the requesting State stating the measures taken or proposes to take, for the prosecution or extradition of that person for that offense, subject to exclude offenses inspired by political motives. It also does not provide a clear procedure for requesting the extradition of a criminal.

Up-to-date information on newly identified Cyberattacks enables the accurate projection of emerging trends and share criminal modus operandi to promote awareness and prevention of attacks such as Ransomware against governments, critical infrastructure, and the healthcare sector, which may cause a major risk and harm to public safety and security (INTERPOL, 2020).

Article 26 of the Budapest Convention states that a Party within the limits of its domestic law and without a prior request shall submit another Party information obtained from its own investigations on offenses established by the Convention when it considers such information might assist the receiving Party and the request is kept confidential. The CCA does not include a spontaneous information procedure, which is essential to prevent targeted cyber attacks. However, a key informant in Technology revealed that Sri Lanka CERT (Computer Emergency Readiness Team) acts as the focal point for sharing spontaneous information. Upon "Easter bombings" in April 2019, spontaneous information helped Sri Lanka to gather electronic evidence, including account details, correspondence successfully, and contents shared through law enforcement agencies under Article 26 of the Convention (Council of Europe, 2020b).

The Budapest Convention Article 27 requires each Party to designate an authority responsible for communicating directly with each other for mutual assistance

requests in the absence of applicable international agreement. CCA does not include a nationally designated authority legally. However, "Sri Lanka CERT works with the Commonwealth Office and the Council of Europe to enhance the country's Cybersecurity ecosystem" (SLCert, 2018b).

The Budapest Convention Article 28 provides provisions for confidentiality and limitations of using the supply of information or material in response to a request made under the Convention's mutual legal assistance, which requires keeping confidential and not used for investigations or proceedings other than those stated in the request. CCA does not include a provision of confidentiality and limitation on information shared under mutual assistance.

Budapest Convention Article 29 on expedited preservation enables a State Party to request another Party for expeditious preservation of stored computer data located within their territory and intention to submit a request for mutual assistance for the search, access, seizure, or disclosure of the data related to an offense. CCA does not include a procedure for expedited preservation of stored computer data on mutual assistance.

The Budapest Convention Article 30 enables a State Party to request another Party to expeditious traffic data preservation concerning specific communication. The transmitted communication path. CCA does not include a procedure for expedited preservation of traffic data on mutual assistance.

The Budapest Convention Article 31 provides Mutual assistance regarding accessing stored computer data that has been preserved under Article 29. CCA does not include a procedure for accessing stored computer data on mutual assistance.

The Budapest Convention Article 32 enables State Party Transborder access to stored computer data with the lawful and voluntary consent of the person who has the lawful authority to disclose the data or where publicly available (open source) without authorization of another Party (Council of Europe, 2013a). It is

questionable whether the provider can consent to disclose a user's data, as in the unsettled *United States v. Microsoft* case (Kyriakides, 2019), where Microsoft refused to provide the data stored outside the United States to the FBI. Article 32 of the Convention allows law enforcement authorities to conduct an extraterritorial investigation in another country without notifying them. It is a question of how a service provider of another country should respond to this nature's situation, which can be considered an intervention of their country's sovereignty. CCA does not include a provision to enable Trans-border access to stored computer data on mutual assistance.

The Budapest Convention Article 33 enables mutual assistance regarding the real-time collection of traffic data associated with their territory transmitted using a computer system on conditions and procedures provided under domestic law. CCA does not include a provision for requesting real-time traffic data on mutual assistance.

The Budapest Convention Article 34 enables mutual assistance regarding the interception of the real-time collection or recording of content data permitted under the applicable treaties and domestic laws. CCA does not include a provision to request real-time content data on mutual assistance.

The Budapest Convention Article 35 requires each State Party to designate a trained and equipped point of contact available on 24 hours and 7 days (24/7) basis to ensure the provision of immediate assistance for the investigations of prescribed offenses, providing technical advice, preservation of data, collection of evidence, provision of legal information, and locating of suspects on an expeditious basis. CCA has not designated a 24/7 point of contact, although Sri Lanka Cert is the focal point for Cybersecurity (SLCert, 2018b).

4.7 Acts of racist and xenophobic nature

The Additional Protocol to the Convention on Cybercrime (Council of Europe, 2003) criminalizes the acts of racist and xenophobic nature committed through computer systems. This provision enables prosecution of dissemination of racist and xenophobic material, racist and xenophobic motivated threats and insults. CCA does not include a similar provision. The key informants in Judiciary and Internet Governance stated that this provision is a timely need to address social media crimes.

4.8 Defamation

Defamation is someone "attacking another's reputation by a false publication or communication to a Third Party tending to bring the person into disrepute" (Britannica, 2020a). As the truth may be difficult and expensive to prove, Cyber defamation cases stand with the protection of opinion, public interest, non-intentional, satire, and freedom of expression (Article 19, 2017). Section 14 of CCA enables awarding compensation to any person or institution for loss or damage consequent to an offense and gaining an economic benefit. However, the terms "loss or damage" in CCA require a clear definition to include physical and logical properties such as intellectual property, reputation, and image as Cyberspace is used to damage an individual's and businesses' reputation with deformation. Such provision can protect against libel, modified images, or videos with intentional deformation.

4.9 Gaps in CCA

Although CCA said to be largely grounded on the Budapest Convention (Council of Europe, 2020b), the research found many gaps in CCA compared to the Convention, especially in investigative procedures, human rights, privacy, and electronic evidence, computer-based crime, and international corporation.

Conspiracy occurs when two or more persons agree to commit a crime; even the contemplated offense has not yet begun. Such an agreement cannot be fulfilled without communication between parties (UNODC, 2018). Offenders use cross border communications in Cyberspace to conspire to commit computer-aided crimes. United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime Article 5, para. 1(a)(i) criminalizes agreeing with one or more other persons intentionally to obtain financial or other material benefits as a crime (UNODC, 2014). Sri Lanka penal code section 113A on conspiracy criminalizes two or more persons agreeing to commit a crime (DSROSL, 1885).

For example, Cultural Property Act No 73 of 1988 prohibits exporting any cultural properties such as antiques older than 100 years from Sri Lanka except upon a license (DSROSL, 1988). However, antiques from Sri Lanka are offered at online sales. Although such publication is not an offense under existing laws, a transaction occurring to export to an international shipping address constitutes an agreement to commit a crime of exporting an antique from Sri Lanka. The CCA needs to consider criminalizing such communications as a conspiracy to commit a crime.

CCA does not clearly define a "lawful authority, " hence require appointing a competent authority. A key informant in Cybersecurity policy stated that "although intervenes in Cybercrime matters on request, Sri Lanka Cert is not legally empowered by an Act of parliament which provides powers needed for effective Cybercrime investigation", confirmed by the key informant in Academia.

Section 10 of the CCA protects information prohibiting any person from disclosing information accessible in a computer without any express authorization. This provision will help protect the business's intellectual properties (Selvakkumaran, 2008), having staff access risk to sensitive information like source codes and personal data. However, it is recommended that this prohibition should be for information declared lawfully confidential, to allow free information flow to expose corruption and wrongdoings through whistleblowing for the public interest. For example, a government employee exposing corrupt practices of an official to the media cannot be held for the prescribed crime of unauthorized disclosure.

Section 12 of the CCA prohibits abetting any offense under this act, and offenders are liable to the same punishment provided for the offense, hence enabling prosecution of organized Cybercrimes. This provision needs expansion to Conspiracy for Cybercrimes, an intent to carry out the offense or an agreement between two or more persons, and solicitation, which can be committed by one person alone (Law Library, 2019).

The Article (17) of CCA provides powers for The Minister to appoint an expert qualified in software or electronic engineering to assist a police officer making the investigation. However, the complexity of Cybercrimes today demands qualifications and skills in the information security discipline. Investigating a sophisticated crime may require multiple experts with technology, business, legal, intelligence, and physiological competencies. Hence a dedicated organization with a team of experts with research capabilities is best suited.

Article 17 (4) of CCA empowers a police officer above the rank of a sub-inspector to lead the investigation with powers to access any information system, computer or computer system, or any program data. However, their competence may not be adequate to search, seize, and preserve electronic evidence in a sophisticated enterprise environment, which may place data integrity at risk, stating the key informant in enterprise technology, hence specifically trained law enforcement

officers with advanced information security competencies should be deployed in investigations.

A problem complained about by citizens is the arbitrary access and search of mobile devices by police officers. However, Article 21 (2) states that no police officer should perform such a function for an investigation under CCA unless the Inspector General of Police has certified in writing that such police officer possesses adequate knowledge and skills in information communication technology and expertise. Hence requires awareness among police officers and the public.

Article 22 of CCA requires a police officer conducting the search and seizure to issue a complete list of items and data, including the date and time of such seizure. In the case of a massive data breach, it would be a horrendous task to create a data list. Hence clear procedures should be provided.

Chapter 5: Conclusion and Recommendations

This research concludes that Cybercrime is a component of a larger crime, a social problem, and a legal one, a threat to public life, business, and government, progressing rapidly across physical and virtual borders, causing serious harm to victims worldwide (ITU, 2012). However, substantive and procedural provisions and mutual legal aspects in the Sri Lankan Computer Crime Legal framework lack comprehensiveness for effectively preventing and prosecution of transnational and transient nature of Cybercrimes. Thus, criminals can take advantage of the weaknesses in enforceability, not exactly complying with the highly sophisticated technology (Abeysekara, 2015), hence recommend harmonizing domestic laws with the Council of Europe's Budapest Convention, providing an effective global legal framework against transnational Cybercrimes.

During this research, limitations occurred in access to policymakers and obtaining perspectives of the general public. The research expanded the author's knowledge and insights on Cybercrimes, human rights, domestic and international legal instruments and suggestions for future research to study, issues of legalizing the protection of critical infrastructure, standards of Cybersecurity, mechanisms for law enforcement, and implications of computer-based crimes on society that may need harmonizing in the legal framework.

5.1 Capacity Building

Most developing countries may not be able to achieve the goal of harmonization of the Budapest Convention without external assistance (Clough, 2015). Therefore Sri Lanka requires a strategic roadmap for the technological, legislative, and institutional capacity building process, including developing necessary skills among investigators, technologists, lawyers, and judges. This process should include resourcing law enforcement officers, standardization, mechanisms for coordination among institutions involved in policy-making, investigations, and Judiciary for effective prevention and fast prosecution of Cybercrimes and (ITU, 2012).

5.2 Electronic evidence

Electronic Transactions Act, No. 19 Of 2006 (DSROSL, 2006) and Evidence (Special Provisions) Act (No. 14 of 1995) (DSROSL, 1995) referred to the admissibility of electronic evidence lack provisions and procedure for digitally signing the evidence, forensic discovery and ensuring of the authenticity of metadata, hence may not be sufficient to deal with complex technical issues involved in the field of evidence related to Cybercrime (Sunday Times, 2009). Therefore, it is essential to enact a comprehensive electronic evidence act covering computer crimes, computer-aided crimes, and crimes in Cyberspace.

5.3 international mutual legal assistance

The existing Cybercrime legislation in Sri Lanka are fragmented, hence lack the capability to address complex, transient, and transnational Cybercrime effectively due to lack of clear provisions and procedures on collecting, preservation, presentation, and archival of electronic evidence, extraterritorial jurisdiction enabled by international mutual legal assistance (UNODC, 2014), 24/7 network, search, seize, interception, Spontaneous information, transborder access inter alia.

5.4 Child pornography and other Cybercrimes

The existing legislation lacks provisions and investigating procedures on crimes related to child pornography, computer forgery, computer fraud, xenophobia (Council of Europe, 2004), identity theft, cryptocurrency, breach of trust, spam, ransomware, cloud computing, Cyber harassment, electronic copyright infringement, Cybersquatting, and electronic money laundering and electronic conspiracy inter alia in Cyberspace.

5.5 Critical Infrastructure

Cybercrime legislations lack provisions and procedures for the protection of critical infrastructure. Hence require enacting laws for this need for national security and stability of the economy. The provisions on critical infrastructure need the inclusion of negligence and recklessness as offenses. The critical infrastructure legislation requires forming an authority with legal powers and effective procedures for enabling due diligence, security standards, and review (ITU, 2012). Capacity building of government institutions responsible for critical infrastructure and training of their staff is equally important.

5.6 Personal data protection

A significant weakness in Cybercrime legislation in Sri Lanka is the lack of personal data protection laws required to ensure citizens' right to privacy (European Union, 2016). It should be noted that personal data protection laws should not hinder the innovation and economic development processes.

5.7 Human rights

Both Cybercrimes, as well as preventive measures, can negatively impact human rights. Hence, Cybercrime legislation and investigative procedures require being mindful of international human rights (Baron, 2002; Council of Europe, 2004; Council of Europe, 2018) to protect the right to privacy, freedom of expression, freedom of assembly, right to work, and right to education and nondiscrimination *inter alia*.

5.8 Public awareness and juvenile justice

The increasing awareness among citizens is important. Research suggests that children getting addicted to the Internet, computers, and mobile phones tend to engage in Cyberbullying, digital piracy, sharing pornography, and hacking with peers (Kalaivani and Kumar, 2017). This requires education and counseling at the school level and amendments to the juvenile justice system to include laws dealing with delinquent conduct by minors on computer-related offenses.

5.9 Multi stakeholder approach for policy making

The weaknesses of Computer Crimes act no 27 of 2007 can be mitigated by creating a broader dialog on a multi-stakeholder platform that enables collaborative policymaking to develop effective Cybercrime strategies, enabling collaboration and cooperation across multiple actors, organizations, and governments, which is now the standard modus operandi for policy development (McGuire, 2000). Hence recommended engaging multi-stakeholders of State, civil society, scientific and technical communities, the business sector, academics, and human rights experts (OHCHR, 2014) for consensus needed in building an effective legislative framework to introduce an effective Cybercrime regime for Sri Lanka.

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Appendix 1.0 : Summary table of main literature

Author and work	Contribution/Thesis/ Central Argument	Perceived Gap in Scholarship
Council of Europe. (2001), Convention on Cybercrime	International treaty for crimes committed via the Internet	Limited ratifications and privacy?
Dailymirror (2018). Status of ICT Laws ‘We’re Incompetent in Dealing with Computer Related Laws .’	Status of computer related laws in Sri Lanka	Human Rights?
Democratic Socialist Republic of Sri Lanka, Computer Crimes Act, No. 24 of 2007 of Sri Lanka	Computer Crimes	Cyber Crimes
European Union. (2013), Cybersecurity Strategy of the European Union – An Open, Safe and Secure Cyberspace	Cybersecurity Strategy	Data Economy?
Fernando, J (2016) The Impact of the Budapest Cybercrime Convention on Sri Lankan Legal System	Sri Lanka became a state party to the Budapest Convention	Data protection and privacy?

Islam, S (2018) Bangladesh Bank Scam	Political interference and the impact of the scam	Inadequacy of data?
Goldstein, K., Ohad, S., Tov, D. and Prazeres, (2018). The Right to Privacy in the Digital Age: Report of the High Commissioner for Human Rights	Right to Privacy	State Sovereignty and Territorial integrity?
Hurst, (2018). Understanding Legal Regimes	Describes Legal Regimes	Cross Border Regimes?
IETF. (2017), Research into Human Rights Protocol Considerations	Human Rights for Internet	Anonymity?
Internet Society (2017). Paths to Our Digital Future	Internet and Society	Legal Aspects?
Internet Society (2018). The Internet and extra-territorial effects of laws	Extra-territorial effects of internet	Territorial Security?
ITU (2012). Understanding Cybercrime: Phenomena, Challenges, and Legal Response	Provides legal aspects of Cybersecurity and to help harmonize legal frameworks	State sovereignty?

Kleijssen, J. and Perri, P. (2017). Cybercrime, Evidence and Territoriality: Issues and Options	Evidence and Territoriality	Sovereignty?
Manap, N. (2015), Cyberspace Identity Theft: An Overview.	Identity Theft	Legal provisions
Morgan, S. (2019). 2019 Official Annual Cybercrime Report	Cybercrime impact on business	Legal remedies?
Robinson, N., Graux, H., Parrilli, D., Klautzer, L. and Valeri, L. (2011). Comparative Study on Legislative and Non Legislative Measures to Combat Identity Theft and Identity Related Crime	Identity Theft	Organized Cyber Crime?
Schmitt, M. et.al. (2009), Tallinn Manual on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Warfare	International law applicable to Cyber conflicts	Non-Binding?
Selvakkumaran, N. (2008). The Legal Regime Governing Computer Crimes : an Appraisal of the	Review of Computer Crime Act	Technology aspects?

Sri Lanka Law.		
Senarathna, I. Warren, M. (2017). A Sri Lankan Hacking Case Study	Information on incident	Legal proceedings?
The White House. (2018), National Cyber Strategy of USA	National Cybersecurity strategies	Dark web's economy and Advanced kill chains?
UNODC. (2013). Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime	Cybercrime studies	Domestic Models
UNHRC, General Comment No. 34	Human Rights on the Internet	Cybercrime Prevention?
United Nations (2001). Responsibility of States for Internationally Wrongful Acts.	Responsibility of States	Legally binding?
Värk, R. (2012). Diplomatic asylum: Theory, Practice and the Case of Julian Assange	The legality of diplomatic asylum	Legally binding obligations?

Appendix 2.0 : Thematic areas for key informant interviews

1. Understanding of Cyber Crime.
2. Gaps in Sri Lankan laws to address Cybercrimes.
3. Understanding of the Budapest Convention.
5. Advantages of the Budapest Convention.
6. Usage of the Budapest Convention in an international legal environment.
7. Sri Lanka trends in Cybercrime Regulations.
8. Budapest Convention experiences in case law development.
9. Challenges in Sri Lanka in adapting to the Budapest Convention.
10. Suggestions for designing an effective Cyber Crime Regime for Sri Lanka.

Appendix 3.0 : Key Informants

- Judiciary
Justice Dr. Ruwan Fernando, Judge of the Court of Appeal, Director, Sri Lanka Judges' Institute

- Cybersecurity Policy
Dr. Kanishka Karunasena, Head Of Research, Policy, and Projects, Sri Lanka CERT|CC

- Legal Practice
Mr. Sunil D. B. Abeyrathna, Senior Attorney-at-Law - Intellectual Property

- Internet Governance
Mr. Maheeswara Kirindigoda, Former Chairman of Internet Society Sri Lanka, Chair Sri Lanka and Vice President Asia Pacific Internet Governance Forum

- Legal Academia
Dr. Thusitha B. Abeysekara, LLM in Computer and Communications Law, LLB, Attorney-at-Law, Legal Studies Unit, Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce, University of Sri Jayewardenepura

- Enterprise Technology
Mr. N. P. Vishva Kumara, Enterprise Technology Consultant

- Information Security
Mt. D Dayalan Nagaratnam, Associate Information Security Engineer, Sri Lanka CERT|CC

